

ACTIVE COMPOSITES AND 4D PRINTING

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ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing, or 3D printing, allows the precise placement of materials at micrometer resolution in a layer-by-layer manner. The recent development of the polyjet techniques admits 3D printing of a solid composed of multiple materials with essentially no or little restrictions on the geometric complexity of their spatial arrangement. Complex 3D solids therefore can be printed with different material distributions in an optimal and controllable fashion, enabling the design and fabrication of parts, devices, and structures with novel multifunctional performance. In this paper, we present the paradigm of printed active composites and 4D printing where the shape of a printed 3D object can change upon external stimuli, thus offering one additional dimension, time, for shape forming and control. We demonstrate this concept by printing shape memory fibers (SMF) in an elastomer matrix to create a composite. After printing, the programming of the SMFs creates time dependence of the composite configuration change. This process has considerable design freedom to enable creation of composites with complex and controllable anisotropic thermomechanical behavior through the fiber architecture design, such as shape, size, orientation and even spatial variation of these parameters. We design and print laminates in thin plate forms that can be programmed to assume complex three-dimensional configurations including bent, coiled, and twisted strips, folded shapes (origami).

1 INTRODUCTION

3D printing, or additive manufacturing (AM), is a layer-by-layer (L-b-L) technique to manufacture three-dimensional (3D) objects directly from a digital model. Unlike conventional subtractive processes that cut away materials, 3D printing builds a finished part in successive layers, therefore offering an obvious potential advantage of saving raw materials and design freedom. 3D printing started about three decades ago and was initially adopted as a high-cost tool for rapid prototyping (RP)[1]. Nowadays, 3D printing has found applications in industries ranging from aerospace to orthodontics[2]. Depending on how raw materials are processed, 3D printing is classified into seven groups by ASTM International Committee F42 on AM Technologies. These include photopolymerization (PP), material extrusion, powder bed fusion, material jetting, binder jetting, sheet lamination, and directed energy deposition. Among these methods, PP can create parts made of crosslinking polymers, which offer a wide range of readily tunable material properties. For example, depending on the glass transition temperature (T_g) and crosslink density, crosslinking polymers can be very soft or stiff at ambient temperature and exhibit excellent thermostability by maintaining their shape at high temperature. In a typical PP-3D printing process, a monomer is polymerized and crosslinked in an L-b-L manner. The parts are created by two methods. The first approach is similar to stereolithography (SLA), where a vat of liquid light curable polymer "resin" is exposed to a rastering laser (or projected light) to build parts one layer at a time. For each layer, the light (laser or patterned source) projects the cross-section of the part pattern on the surface of the liquid resin. Exposure to the light cures and solidifies the pattern traced on the resin and joins it to the layer below. The SLA's elevator platform then descends by a distance equal to the thickness of a single layer, followed by a

resin-filled blade sweeping across the cross-section of the part, re-coating it with fresh material. The second approach is inkjet based 3D printing (Figure 1). It uses inkjets to selectively deposit droplets of liquid resin onto a building platform. A precision roller levels the droplets, resulting in a uniform thickness (~16-50 μm) layer and then a laser raster scan is used to harden the liquid resin. After one layer is cured, the second layer is deposited then cured by repeating the above process. The advantage of inkjet 3D printing is that multiple inkjet heads with different polymer resin inks can be used to enable the multi-material 3D printing (Figure 1), which enables great design flexibility.

Figure 1. A schematic graph of polyjet printing process where several inkjet heads are used to controls the detailed formation of the part.

In this paper, we report our recent work[3, 4] of using a multi-material 3D printing to demonstrate the 4D printing concept through printed active composites (PAC). This process allows the fabrication of a solid from a digital design with properties that vary from a void to an elastomer to a stiff plastic (and everything in between). The printed laminates are soft composites consisting of glassy polymer fibers reinforcing an elastomeric matrix where the glassy polymer fibers have shape memory effects to serve as a switch to trigger the shape change of the composite. They can then be thermo-mechanically programmed to assume complex three-dimensional configurations including bent, coiled, and twisted strips, folded shapes.

2 FABRICATION AND MATERIALS

In this paper, we print a composite with long fibers (Figure 2). The sample thickness, fiber diameters, space, and orientation are defined through a CAD drawing. Our strategy to create PACs is to use a matrix material, which is elastomeric over our desired operating temperature range of between room temperature and about 60°C, and to use fibers that exhibit the shape memory effect (SME) over this temperature range. Thus we design our PACs to have a matrix with a glass transition temperature (T_g) below 25°C and the fibers to exhibit SME in the range 25°C to 70°C. To this end we make use of the digital materials that are available with a multi-material 3D printer (Objet 260 Connex, Stratasys, Edina, MN, USA). The layer by layer printing process works by depositing droplets of polymer ink onto the building platform, wiping them into a smooth film, and Ultra-Violet (UV) photopolymerizing the film. Once a layer is created, the platform moves down and the next layer is printed. Several inkjet heads with separate material sources exist in the printing block, and so multiple materials can be printed in each layer, which is nominally 64 μm thick. In our work, each layer generally contains both the matrix and the fibers. The Object printer provides two base materials: one is called TangoBlack, which is rubbery at room temperature, and the other one is called VeroWhite, which is a rigid plastic at room temperature. The printer can also print digital materials that consist of varying compositions of these two materials that lead to different thermomechanical properties. In this paper, we created printed active composite consisting of TangoBlack as the matrix and a digital material (termed Gray 60). Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) tests showed that the peaks of $\tan\delta$ curves are at ~ -5 °C for

TangoBlack, and ~ 47 °C for Gray 60, indicating the glass transition temperature of these two materials are at -5 °C and ~ 47 °C, respectively.

Figure 2. A schematic graph of the printed active composite[3].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Samples with different fiber layouts are printed and investigated. The results are presented below. More information can be found in our recent work[3, 4].

3.1 Orientation dependent modulus

We first tested the 3D printed composites, whose fibers are at the middle plane of the lamina. We vary the fiber orientation to observe the variation of the modulus of the printed composite. Figure 3 shows the modulus as a function of the fiber angle, which is defined in Figure 2.

Figure 3. The dependence of modulus of the printed composite of the fiber orientation[3]. Dots represent the experimental results. Lines are from theoretical predictions.

In Figure 3, dots represent the experimental results and the lines are theoretical predictions, which are developed based on the recent theories of fiber-reinforced elastomers by Guo et al.[5, 6], Lopez-Pamies et al.[7], deBotton et al.[8]. The theory describes the experiments well and both show significant anisotropy in the response. Theoretical predictions also show the modulus variations at different fiber volume fractions. The modulus increases as the fiber volume fraction increases but the dependence on the fiber orientation shows the same trend as that of the printed samples.

3.2 Anisotropic shape memory effects

Since the fibers can have shape memory effects in the temperature range from below the T_g to above T_g , we explore the shape memory effects of the lamina as a function of the fiber orientations. Here, we apply a typical thermomechanical loading cycle for shape memory polymers, i.e., the lamina is first heated to a temperature (65°C) above the T_g of the fiber and stretched. While holding the load, the sample is cooled to 15°C at a rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. After further holding the sample for 5min, the sample is released and the deformation of the sample is recorded. Finally, the sample is heated to the high temperature (65°C) again.

Figure 4. (Top) The deformation history of the printed lamina during a shape memory thermomechanical loading cycle. (Bottom) Shape fixity as a function of fiber orientation.

Figure 4 shows the deformation history of the lamina as a function of time during a shape memory cycle. It can be seen that as the sample is unloaded at low temperature, a temporary shape fixed. The amount of the deformation being fixed depends on the fiber orientation. The dependence of shape fixing capability of the lamina on the fiber orientation can be clearly observed in the bottom plots in Figure 4. The largest shape fixing occurs when the fiber is along the stretching direction (fiber angle of 0°). However, it is also interesting to note that even at fiber of 90° , the temporary can still be fixed. This is mainly due to the Poisson's effect. It is also interesting to note that the lowest shape fixing capability occurs around the fiber orientation of $45\text{-}60^\circ$.

3.3 Laminate behavior and 4D printing

We further design the printed laminate. Here, the so-called laminate is not achieved by gluing two sheets of laminae together; instead, we simply draw a thin sheet where the top and bottom of the sheet have different fiber volume fractions and orientations. In this work, we make the top layer have no fibers and vary the fiber orientation in the bottom layer (Figure 5a).

Figure 5. a) Schematic graphs of the active laminate. b) A laminate strip. c) After thermomechanical programming, the strip deforms into different shapes, depending on the arrangement of the shape memory fibers.

The printed laminates appear to be similar (Figure 5b), but after the thermomechanical programming, they deform into different shapes, depending on the arrangement for the shape memory fibers. For the coiled shape in Figure 5c-1, the fibers are arranged along the strip axial direction; for the collapsed shape in Figure 5c-2, the fibers are in perpendicular direction of the strip axis; for the helical shape in Figure 5c-3, the fibers are 45° away from the axial direction; and for the sinusoidal shape in Figure 5c-4, the fibers are placed in the top and bottom layers alternatively.

Figure 6. Printed active origami. a) Schematic graphs of hinge design. b) The printed thin sheet with hinges (black color regions). c) After programming, the thin sheet deforms into an airplane.

3.4 Active origami

The printed active composite can generate bending deformation, which can be used as hinges to create folding. We thus utilize PAC to create active origami. Figure 6a shows the hinge design. Here the PAC is used as the hinge, which is attached to two rigid panels (using VeroWhite). The printed thin sheet is shown in Figure 6b. It contains hinge regions (black color regions in the figure). Upon the thermomechanical programming, the thin sheet folds into a small airplane shape.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the concept of 4D printing is demonstrated using printed active composites. Here, the composite obtains its active motion through embedding shape memory fibers. The composite design can be directly printed by a multi-material 3D printer. The shape change of the composite is achieved through a post-printing thermomechanical programming. A variety of shape changes can be obtained, depending on the fiber arrangement. Therefore, one can extend the concept of 4D printing to general spatial variations of materials properties and use computational design tools such as shape and topology optimization to design the layout of the materials in the composite, as well as exploit instabilities to create large configurational changes.

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